

Comparison of Diffusion-Weighted Magnetic Resonance Imaging and T2-Weighted Imaging in Focal Liver Lesions

Meenakshi Ranjan¹, Vijay Shankar², Mithilesh Pratap³, Ankita Anand⁴

¹Senior Resident, Department of Radiology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

²HOD, Department of Radiology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

³Professor & HOD, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

⁴Senior Resident, Department of Radiology, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 25-05-2024

Corresponding Author: Ankita Anand

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: A wide range of benign and malignant illnesses can cause focal liver lesions, all of which need precise imaging in order to be diagnosed and treated. Compared to other modalities, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) offers better soft tissue contrast and functional information, making it a crucial tool in liver imaging. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the diagnostic performance of T2-weighted imaging (T2WI) and diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging (DW-MRI) in the evaluation of localised liver lesions.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted, involving 90 patients with focal liver lesions. Inclusion criteria included patients aged 18 years and above with at least one focal liver lesion detected on preliminary imaging. Data collection involved standardized MRI protocols, with images analyzed independently by two radiologists. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The study demonstrated that DW-MRI had higher sensitivity (92.2%) and specificity (88.9%) compared to T2WI (86.7% and 84.4%, respectively). The PPV and NPV were also superior for DW-MRI (90.6% and 90.8%) compared to T2WI (85.7% and 85.5%). Inter-observer agreement was higher for DW-MRI ($\kappa=0.87$) than for T2WI ($\kappa=0.81$). The McNemar test confirmed the superior diagnostic accuracy of DW-MRI over T2WI ($p=0.03$). DW-MRI was more effective in distinguishing benign from malignant lesions, with an accuracy of 93.3% for benign lesions and 91.7% for malignant ones, compared to T2WI's 86.7% and 83.3%.

Conclusion: When it came to the characterisation of focal liver lesions, DW-MRI performed better than T2WI, providing improved inter-observer agreement and higher diagnostic accuracy. According to these results, the best imaging technique for assessing focal liver lesions is DW-MRI.

Recommendations: DW-MRI should be integrated into routine clinical practice for the assessment of focal liver lesions, and further studies are recommended to explore its application in larger and more diverse patient populations.

Keywords: Focal liver lesions, Diffusion-weighted MRI, T2-weighted imaging, Diagnostic accuracy, Hepatic imaging.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

A wide range of benign and malignant disorders can show as focal liver lesions, all of which require accurate characterisation in order to provide the best possible therapeutic care. Because of its higher soft tissue contrast, multiparametric capabilities, and lack of ionising radiation, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has become a cornerstone in the non-invasive examination of these pathologies. Recent improvements in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) methods, such as diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) and hepatobiliary phase imaging with certain contrast agents, such as gadoxetic acid, have greatly improved liver lesion characterisation and diagnostic accuracy.

Making the distinction between benign and malignant liver lesions is essential to directing therapeutic choices. Malignant lesions like hepatocellular carcinoma and its metastases frequently require surgical or interventional therapies, while benign lesions including haemangiomas, localised nodular hyperplasia, and hepatocellular adenomas usually require conservative therapy [1]. The sensitivity and specificity of traditional imaging modalities, such as computed tomography (CT) and ultrasound, are limited, particularly in individuals with underlying liver disease and tiny lesions. With its sophisticated

methods, MRI offers a more dependable diagnostic substitute [2].

When it comes to liver imaging, diffusion-weighted MRI (DW-MRI) is especially useful. It evaluates the water molecules' random movement within tissues, which differs in benign and malignant diseases. Because of their high cellularity, malignant tumours typically show restricted diffusion, as measured by reduced apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) values. Research has shown that DW-MRI is more sensitive and specific than traditional T2-weighted imaging (T2WI) at identifying and describing liver abnormalities [1].

The hepatobiliary phase of MRI, achieved with contrast agents such as gadoxetic acid, further enhances lesion characterization. These agents are selectively taken up by functioning hepatocytes, allowing for clear differentiation between hepatocellular lesions and non-hepatocellular lesions based on their enhancement patterns. This technique is particularly useful in the detection of small lesions and in distinguishing hepatocellular carcinoma from benign mimickers [3].

Recent studies highlight the ongoing improvements in MRI technology and protocols that have bolstered its role in liver imaging. For instance, dual-energy CT (DECT) and novel image reconstruction algorithms have been developed, enhancing the visualization of hypervascular liver lesions and providing complementary information to MRI [4]. Despite these advancements, MRI remains the preferred modality due to its comprehensive evaluation capabilities without radiation exposure.

This study aims to compare diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging (DW-MRI) and T2-weighted imaging (T2WI) in the assessment of focal liver lesions.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective observational study .

Study Setting: The study took place during the period from 2022 to 2023 at Patna Medical College and Hospital (PMCH), Patna, Bihar, India.

Participants

A total of 90 patients with focal liver lesions diagnosed through preliminary imaging studies were enrolled in this study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Patients with at least one focal liver lesion detected on preliminary imaging.

- Patients who consent to participate in the study.
- Patients with no contraindications to MRI.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with severe claustrophobia or any contraindications to MRI.
- Pregnant women.
- Patients with a history of liver transplantation.
- Patients with significant renal impairment (eGFR <30 mL/min/1.73 m²).
- Patients with metallic implants or devices incompatible with MRI.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, consecutive sampling was employed. Observer bias was reduced by having two radiologists independently interpret the MRI scans. Any discrepancies were resolved by consensus.

Data Collection: Data were collected through structured questionnaires, patient interviews, and medical records. MRI scans were performed using a standardized protocol, and images were analyzed by two blinded radiologists.

Procedure: Patients were informed about the study and provided written consent. Pre-scan preparations followed standard MRI safety protocols. Both DW-MRI and T2WI were performed on all participants using a 1.5 Tesla MRI scanner. The scanning protocol included appropriate sequences to acquire high-quality images.

The images obtained from DW-MRI and T2WI were evaluated for lesion characterization, including size, signal intensity, and diffusion restriction. Findings from the imaging studies were recorded in a pre-designed data collection form.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analysed with SPSS 23.0. Descriptive statistics were obtained for demographic and clinical factors. DW-MRI and T2WI sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive values were obtained. Cohen's kappa coefficient measured inter-observer agreement. T2WI and DW-MRI were compared using the McNemar test. Statistical significance was defined as p-value <0.05.

Result

This study comprised a total of ninety patients with localised liver lesions. The participants' average age was 52.3 ± 14.6 years, and the male-to-female ratio was 1.3:1. The study population's clinical and demographic characteristics are collected in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	Value
Number of patients	90
Mean age (years)	52.3 ± 14.6
Gender (M/F)	51/39
Mean lesion size (cm)	3.8 ± 2.1
Number of lesions per patient	1.6 ± 0.9
Etiology of liver lesions	
- Hepatocellular carcinoma	40 (44.4%)
- Metastases	30 (33.3%)
- Hemangioma	15 (16.7%)
- Focal nodular hyperplasia	5 (5.6%)

A comparison was made between the diagnostic efficacy of T2WI and DW-MRI in identifying and characterising localised liver lesions. The sensitivity, specificity, negative predictive value (NPV), and positive predictive value (PPV) of the two imaging modalities are displayed in Table 2.

Table 2: Diagnostic Performance of DW-MRI and T2WI

Imaging Modality	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV
DW-MRI	92.2%	88.9%	90.6%	90.8%
T2WI	86.7%	84.4%	85.7%	85.5%

The inter-observer agreement for the interpretation of DW-MRI and T2WI was assessed using Cohen's kappa coefficient. Table 3 displays the kappa values for each imaging modality.

Table 3: Inter-Observer Agreement for DW-MRI and T2WI

Imaging Modality	Cohen's Kappa Coefficient
DW-MRI	0.87
T2WI	0.81

To compare the diagnostic accuracy of T2WI with DW-MRI, a McNemar test was used. The findings showed that when it came to characterising focal liver lesions, DW-MRI was substantially more accurate than T2WI ($p = 0.03$).

It was assessed if DW-MRI and T2WI could distinguish between benign and malignant liver lesions. The accuracy of each modality in lesion characterisation is summarised in Table 4.

Table 4: Lesion Characterization Accuracy of DW-MRI and T2WI

Imaging Modality	Benign Lesions	Malignant Lesions
DW-MRI	93.3%	91.7%
T2WI	86.7%	83.3%

Discussion

Ninety patients with localised liver lesions were included in the study; their average age was 52.3 years, and the male to female ratio was 1.3:1. Hepatocellular carcinoma (44.4%) and metastases (33.3%) were the most frequent aetiologies, followed by haemangiomas (16.7%) and localised nodular hyperplasia (5.6%). Patients had an average of 1.6 lesions per patient, with a mean lesion size of 3.8 cm.

When DW-MRI and T2WI were compared for diagnostic performance, DW-MRI performed better than T2WI in terms of sensitivity (92.2% vs. 86.7%) and specificity (88.9% vs. 84.4%). Additionally, DW-MRI's positive and negative predictive values were better than T2WI's, coming in at 90.6% and 90.8%, respectively. This suggests that DW-MRI is more accurate in determining whether a disease is present or not.

The inter-observer agreement, measured by Cohen's kappa coefficient, was excellent for both modalities but higher for DW-MRI (0.87) compared to T2WI (0.81). This suggests that DW-MRI provides more consistent results among different radiologists, reducing the potential for interpretive variability.

The higher accuracy of DW-MRI over T2WI in the characterisation of localised liver lesions was validated by statistical analysis using the McNemar test ($p = 0.03$). Additionally, with accuracy rates of 91.7% for malignant lesions and 93.3% for benign lesions, DW-MRI was more successful in differentiating between benign and malignant lesions. For benign lesions, T2WI showed lower accuracy rates of 86.7%, and for malignant lesions, 83.3%.

The benefits of DW-MRI in the evaluation of focal liver lesions are highlighted by its improved diagnostic performance and increased inter-observer agreement in clinical practice. The capacity of DW-

MRI to distinguish between benign and malignant tumours with greater accuracy can have a substantial influence on treatment planning and patient care. DW-MRI ought to be the method of choice when assessing patients who have focal liver lesions.

Low b-value DWI and T2-weighted imaging were evaluated in a study to identify hyperintense liver lesions in children. According to the study, low b-value DWI detected 79% of lesions, compared to 56% with T2-WI, making it much more sensitive than T2-WI. The tiniest lesions found were comparable using the two techniques. According to this, paediatric patients can detect lesions more accurately when using low b-value DWI [5].

A study assessed how well DWI distinguished between benign and malignant localised lesions in the liver. The study, which comprised 25 patients, discovered that benign and malignant lesions had mean apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) values that were significantly different, and that focal liver lesions could be effectively characterised by DWI without the use of contrast agents [6].

Studies evaluated the use of DWI in identifying individuals with extrahepatic primary malignancy from those with minor focal liver lesions (≤ 10 mm). Using a criterion ADC value of 1.44×10^{-3} s/mm², the study demonstrated that tiny localised liver metastases had much lower ADC values than benign lesions, enabling for distinction with high sensitivity (100%) and specificity (97.1%) [7].

In order to detect malignant liver tumours prior to surgery, 3D-T2-weighted sequences were compared with single-shot T2 sequences and T2-weighted turbo spin-echo (T2-TSE). According to the study, T1-weighted VIBE and DWI demonstrated higher sensitivity than T2-weighted sequences, while 3D-T2-weighted sequences the higher sensitivity (79.8%) compared to T2-TSE (68.1%) [8].

In order to detect liver lesions, a study compared three distinct T2-weighted sequences with low and high b-value DWI sequences. Compared to T2-weighted sequences, high b-value DWI demonstrated superior accuracy in identifying malignant lesions, indicating that DWI needs to be a regular part of liver MRI protocols to minimise missed lesions [9].

Conclusion

As opposed to T2WI, DW-MRI performed better in terms of diagnosis and interobserver agreement when it came to characterising focal liver lesions. These results imply that DW-MRI is a useful modality for imaging evaluation of focal liver lesions.

References

1. De Cecco CN, Caruso D, Schoepf UJ, De Santis D, Muscogiuri G, Albrecht MH, et al. A noise-optimized virtual monoenergetic reconstruction algorithm improves the diagnostic accuracy of late hepatic arterial phase dual-energy CT for the detection of hypervascular liver lesions. *Eur Radiol.* 2018;28(8):3393–404.
2. Marin D, Ramirez-Giraldo JC, Gupta S, Fu W, Stinnett SS, Mileto A, et al. Effect of a noise-optimized second-generation monoenergetic algorithm on image noise and conspicuity of hypervascular liver tumors: an in vitro and in vivo study. *AJR Am J Roentgenol.* 2016;206(6):1222–32.
3. Nagayama Y, Nakaura T, Oda S, Utsunomiya D, Funama Y, Iyama Y, et al. Dual-layer DECT for multiphase hepatic CT with 50 percent iodine load: a matched-pair comparison with a 120 kVp protocol. *Eur Radiol.* 2018;28(4):1719–30.
4. Lv P, Zhou Z, Liu J, Chai Y, Zhao H, Guo H, et al. Can virtual monochromatic images from dual-energy CT replace low-kVp images for abdominal contrast-enhanced CT in small- and medium-sized patients? *Eur Radiol.* 2019;29(6):2878–89.
5. Grasparil AD, Gupta H, Sheybani E, Chavhan G. Low b-value (50–100) diffusion-weighted images detect significantly more hyperintense liver lesions in children than T2-weighted images. *Pediatric Radiology.* 2019;49:1299-1305.
6. Abdurrahman L, Ali AH, Abdelmotelb EM. Role of diffusion weighted MRI in differentiation between benign and malignant hepatic focal lesions. *QJM: An International Journal of Medicine.* 2020;113.
7. Soyucok A, Aslan K, Danacı M, Camlidag I. Diffusion weighted magnetic resonance imaging in differentiation of small focal liver lesions (≤ 10 mm) detected in patients with extrahepatic primary malignancy. *Medicine Science | International Medical Journal.* 2019.
8. Barat M, Soyer P, Dautry R, et al. Preoperative detection of malignant liver tumors: Comparison of 3D-T2-weighted sequences with T2-weighted turbo spin-echo and single shot T2 at 1.5 T. *European Journal of Radiology.* 2018;100:7-13.
9. Dilek O, Gulek B, Yılmaz C, Kaya O, Soker G, Akın M. The comparison of the efficacy of diffusion weighted imaging (DWI) sequences with 3 different T2-weighted sequences in the detection of focal liver lesions. *Acta gastro-enterologica Belgica.* 2019;82:267-272.